

Current Road Transportation Issue and Development in Purba Medinipur District of West Bengal

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Abstract

Since road transport is the major means of transportation of the goods and peoples in the district, the study of transport will obviously be concentrated on the road ways. An appraisal of the changing pattern of roads transportation in different periods is essential for full understanding of the present day features. It also provides key for visualizing and moderating the future trends for the pattern of circulation which is regarded as a unifying bond between inter period as well as inter regional relationship. The objective of the present study is to analyze the trend, growth, problems of road transport and variation in road network in the district of Purba Medinipur with the help of secondary data. Road networks in the district consisting of (1) National highways (NHs), (2) State highways (SHs), (3) major district roads (MDRs), and (4) rural roads (RRs) that include other district roads and village roads. The growth rate of road was 14.21 per cent in 2021 due to significant increase in urban roads. The road density has increased from 3.28 km in 2001 to 3.96 km in 2012 and 4.28 km in 2021 registering a CAGR of 3.9%. The study also aims at providing a base towards thorough study of micro level road transport planning of the district to serve as a background for the study of rural development in terms of broad regional development.

Keywords Road Transportation, Pattern of Circulation, Micro Level Planning, Regional Development.

Introduction

The road transport infrastructure is fundamental to economic growth. Poor road infrastructure affects economic growth in rural areas. It impacts negatively on domestic and local trade, on the final cost of goods, competition and competitiveness, logistics in general, movement of people, inward investment opportunities, and ultimately on employment. The immediate output of the road infrastructure development is better and more efficient physical infrastructure which will lead to improve connectivity between rural and urban communities, and through this, to greater access to markets and economic activity in general. Improved connectivity will reduce the cost of final goods, entice inward investment, and create jobs in rural areas. Infrastructure contributes to poverty reduction and better living standards. The rural sector will remain the mainstay of the economy in West Bengal. In rural areas roads are constructed to enhance the rural connectivity by connecting the unconnected habitations.

Aim of study

The present study is an attempt to analyse the existing road network of the district as well as to examine the impacts of the road network on economic infrastructure and regional development by evaluating economic and social benefits in Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal. The broad objectives are given below:

- i. Systematic and integrated study of road connectivity system of Purba Medinipur district at block level.
- ii. Understanding an in-depth analysis of the said road network structure and its role in the regional economy and subsequent overall development of the district.

iii. To evaluate the developmental impact of roads in terms of change in income, borrowings, physical capital of households, distance to various places, in the study area.

iv. Developing a comprehensive idea of road connectivity characteristics at district level and problem to serve as a background for planning the future road transport network for more effective use of resources as a necessary for balanced development of the district.

Review of Literature

An extensive literature review has been made in the present study. Many social scientists have studied the structure of transport networks using graph theoretical techniques. Garrison (1960) has applied some of the techniques of graph theory to analyse the connectivity of inter-state highway system of the U.S.A. for the year 1957. Garrison and Marble (1961.) have designed a set of measures based on concepts of the graph theory. These measures deal with the theoretical and empirical investigations of what has been termed as structure of transport network. Nystuen and Dacey (1961) analyzed the functional connections between central places based upon communication follows in a network with the help of graph theoretic measures to regional highway network. Kansky (1963) has undertaken an extensive empirical analysis of transport network structure and suggested a number of measures for analyzing complex transport network structures. Kissling has examined (1969) the regional highway network for the province of Nova Scotia and has used it to identify the probable growth points in the systems and more particularly to pinpoint the existing bottlenecks where improvement would yield greater benefits to the region. V.L. Singh, D. k. Singh, and J.K. Rautray, H. Ramehandran (1973) and M. Raza (1980) have also studied the graph theoretic measures related to the Indian transportation system and have suggested some developmental measures based on the analysis for improvement of the transport efficiency particularly in properly connected areas of the country. These studies affirm the applicability at the analytical approach and of graph theoretic techniques to the analysis of transport network.

According to Aderamo (2003), road network constitutes an important element in urban development as roads provide accessibility required by different land uses and the proper functioning of such urban areas depends on efficient transport network, which is a backbone to their very existence. The analysis of the road network involves the recognition of the patterns and qualities of the roads. Topology, according to Xie and Levinson (2006), is an arrangement and connectivity of nodes and links of measuring the spatial structure while configuration refers to collection of objects that comprise the pattern of road networks. In computing density, the network indicator approach was used to partition road network into different parts in reasonable way before the roads inside each part were extracted and the density calculated using indirectly related parameters. This results in number of connections to describe density differences in road networks.

The recent findings in the study of networks are quite promising for the future of the network science community. De Bona et al. (2021) used weighted and unweighted network of a transportation network where nodes are the stations and a links are any number of routes connecting two nodes. Weighted networks were built using the geographical distances between two stations.

The various theories and concepts have been reviewed in order to set the foundation on which the present study is founded. A review of literature on earlier works was carried out with gaps in such studies identified. Some of the works and theories emphasized that the more accessible location is the better a location is connected in terms of network of access roads and has better developmental aspects.

Methodology

The present research work has been based on data collected from primary and secondary sources. While the primary data were collected by administering structured questionnaires, using intensive interviews and primary surveys. The structured questionnaire was administered to the sample population of the selected rural areas in the Purba Medinipur district. Secondary data were gathered from various published and unpublished records, books and journals and various institutions of both state and central government's reports and journals. Both quantitative and qualitative studies have been followed throughout the study. For analyzing the network structure, emphasis has been given on cartographic representation and Computation.

Analysis

Location of the Study Area:

Purba Medinipur District came into existence after bifurcation of erstwhile Midnapur on and from January 1, 2002. This district is situated on the southern side of the State of West Bengal. The total area of the district is 4,151.64 square kilometers. It is situated between 21°38' N to 22°31' N and 87°27' E to 88°12' E. The District is surrounded by Ghatal Sub-division of Paschim Medinipur District in the north, Bay of Bengal in the south, Paschim Medinipur district in the west and Hoogly-Rupnarayan river in the east

(Rupnarayan river separates this district from Howrah). are its. The district comprises of 4 Subdivisions (Tamluk, Haldia, Contai and Egra), 25 Blocks and 5 Municipalities, namely Panskura,Tamluk, Egra, Contai and Haldia.

Figure No: 1- Location Map

6. Road Transport system in Purba Midnapur district:

The roads system in Purba Medinipur district reflect the present position of the road transport network which actually provides a good impression of the communication linkage by roads of all categories in the district. The road network system in the district is categorized in to-

There are only three National High ways passing through the district, 1) N.H.-41; extending from Kolaghat to Haldia covering length of 61 km and 2) N.H.-06; extending from Kolaghat to Mechchogram having a length of 16 km and 3) N.H.- 116B extending from Nandakumar to Digha covers 90 km length.

Table No- 1: National High Ways in Purba Medinipur district

No. of Roads	Extension	Nature	Length
01.	Kolaghat to Haldia (N.H. - 41)	04 lane	61km
02.	Kolaghat to Mechogram (N.H. - 06)	Six lane	16km
03.	Nandakumar to Digha (N.H.- 116B)	04 lane	90 km

Source: National High way Authority of India.

As per P.W.D. (Roads) record there is five State High Ways in the district of Purba Medinipur covering total length of 201 km. These roads contribute a lot to the regional development of the district. A brief description of the major State High Ways of the district has been given in table.

Table: 2: Major State Highway of the district

SI No.	Extension	Nature of the road	Len2th
01	Contai By pass Road	State Highway No.4	3 km
02	Digha - Foreshore Road	State Highway No.4	6 km
03	Panskura-Durgachack	State Highway No.4	69 km
04	Contai to Belda	State Highway No.4A	58Km
05	Egra to Bajkul	State Highway No.4	52Km
06	Contai- Junput	State Highway No.4A	9km

Source: Superintending Engineer, State High Way Circle No. 06, PWD (Roads) Directorate

Besides state high ways, there are seven district roads. The major district roads are i) Egra-Bajkul Road covering a length of 52 Km, ii) Egra- Ramnagar Road having a length of 27 km and iii) Chaitanyapur-Balughata Road covering a length of only 9.20 Km. A brief description of other district roads are given in table no. 3.

Table No- 3: Major District Roads

SI No.	Extension	Nature of the road	Length
01	Egra -.Bajkul	Major District Road	52Km
02	Egra -Ramnagar	Major District Road	27Km
03	Chaityanapur- Balughata	Major District Road	9.20Km

SI No.	Extension	Nature of the road	Len2th
01	Mohanpur to Solpatta	Other than District Road	22.65 Km
02	Contai to Junput	Other than District I Road	9.4Km
03	Tamluk Diversion Road	Other than District I Road	3.21 km
04	Mecheda Tamluk Road	Other than District Road	14.40 Km

Source: Superintending Enginee1; State High Way Circle No. 06, PWD (Roads) Directorate
Village Roads:

The village roads in Purba Medinipur district are mainly maintained by Panchayets, Panchayet Samities and zila parishad. These village roads are of mainly two types; - one is the surface and another is un-surface roads. About 481 km roads have been constructed as metaled roads under Prime Minister Gram Sarak Yoyona (PMGSY). PMGSY are the landmark for the development of road transportation in the district which

actually have tremendous economic growth power. Most of the village's roads are concrete roads which are maintained by Panchayets and Panchayet samities. In this study the except PMGSY roads other village roads have not been considered. Beside this above mentioned roads there are some roads which actually built and maintained by fishery department facilitating in movements towards fishing grounds. Similarly some roads are maintained.

These roads facilitated movement of the local people and local resources. Thus roads have significant impact on the development of the rural economy of the district. Obviously the un-surfaced roads of the district play a significant role in the movement of people and goods.

Table No- 4: Rural roads of Purba Medinipur district.

Sl no.	Village road type	length
1	Village road constructed by Zilaparishad	241km
2	Rural road constructed under PMGSY	481km
3	Other village road	76.46 km